

Humboldt Union in Bulgaria

Unterstützt von / Supported by

Alexander von Humboldt
Stiftung/Foundation

SCIENCE WITHOUT BORDERS: ALEXANDER VON HUMBOLDT'S CONCEPTS IN TODAY'S WORLD

PROCEEDINGS OF THE HUMBOLDT-KOLLEG
Varna, September 18 – 21, 2019

Edited by

*Lora Taseva, Radka Argirova, Dilyana Boteva,
Maria Luisa Grilli and Tăchiță Vlad-Bubulac*

Sofia 2020

The publication of this volume was supported by
the Alexander von Humboldt Foundation
Germany

INTRINSIC PHYSICAL BARRIER QUALITY OF PLUTONIUM PRODUCED IN PRESSURISED WATER REACTORS

Ivaylo Naydenov

Keywords: *proliferation resistance, plutonium, nuclear fuel cycle*

Abstract: *In recent years, non-proliferation of nuclear materials has become an important issue, regarding civilian fuel cycle development. In addition, future advancement in nuclear energy systems and nuclear fuel cycles should comply with non-proliferation criteria. These requirements stem from the circumstance that nuclear power is considered to be a dual purpose technology. There is an ongoing debate about the usability of reactor-grade plutonium in nuclear explosives manufacturing. Moreover, there is no universally recognized and verified methodology for proliferation resistance assessment. On the other hand, intrinsic material factors may play a further role in strengthening fuel cycles' proliferation resistance, since the majority of the efforts in that area so far have been focused on enhancing technical barriers. The current paper represents a synthesis of the main results obtained by applying different methodologies for proliferation properties evaluation, published separately.*

Introduction

The relevance of the problems associated with the non-proliferation of nuclear materials is defined by the following circumstances: (1) nuclear power is considered to be a dual-purpose technology (Kang 2005), and (2) the probability for proliferation creates certain obstacles for nuclear power development in terms of creating negative perception of nuclear technology (Ezoubtchenko et al. 2005). Proliferation resistance is among the core principles of nuclear power development and is an objective that should be fulfilled by advanced fuel cycles (IAEA 2008; IAEA 2013). Proliferation resistance also represents a necessary condition, set forth by the European Commission, which needs to be met in order to guarantee the future advancement of nuclear energy in the European Union (European Commission 2016). It is thought that proliferation of nuclear materials is one of the most important problems facing the future progress of nuclear energy (Kimura et al. 2011).

The main concerns about possible proliferation risk increase are based on the global plutonium inventory that is estimated to be increasing at a rate of about 60 tonnes per annum (Beller, Krakowski 1999: 3). Plutonium is considered to be among the most important materials from non-proliferation perspective (Kimura et al. 2011). In order to define the level of usability of civilian plutonium for nuclear explosive device construction, it is necessary to analyse those properties of the material that could make it suitable for non-civilian applications. Most often, the attributes linked to a material's proliferation resistance are the bare critical mass of a sphere, its decay heat, the spontaneous neutron emission, and the radiological barrier (Beller, Krakowski 1999: 3; Ezoubtchenko et al. 2005; IAEA 2010: 5–6). These factors compose the so-called isotopic barrier to proliferation. Some of the factors influence the material's usability, others – the probability for acquisition, transportation, and reprocessing (Skutnik, Yim 2011).

The non-proliferation of nuclear materials is defined by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) as a property of a nuclear system or facility that impedes nuclear material's diversion and/or undeclared production, as well as malicious applications of nuclear technology by a state aiming to acquire nuclear weapons or other nuclear explosive devices. This definition implies that proliferation resistance is a measure of the difficulties that should be overcome in order to develop and/or acquire nuclear weapons or nuclear explosive devices by means of a civilian fuel cycle and civilian technologies. These difficulties include, but are not limited to, technical and technological barriers, required skills, time, etc. Misusing a nuclear fuel cycle could include usage of materials, equipment, technological processes, facilities, and knowledge related to the civilian fuel cycle (IAEA 2010: 2, 4). In the case of nuclear proliferation, there is misuse of nuclear material and/or nuclear facilities by the host state (Bathke et al. 2009).

The proliferation barriers can be divided in intrinsic and extrinsic (IAEA 2010: 5; Skutnik, Yim 2011). The intrinsic barriers may be physical – related to the properties of the material, and technical – related to the properties of the nuclear facilities, the access to the facilities, and the availability of specialists with adequate knowledge and skills, and time for device development (IAEA 2010: 5). The most important factors of the intrinsic barrier are linked to the material's properties; in total, the isotopic, chemical, radiological, and weight factors have a relative share of 63.5 %. Another significant factor, with a relative weight of 18.1 %, is the available inventory (Skutnik, Yim 2011).

Methods

The presented assessments are carried out using two methodologies – the ‘Figure of Merit’ methodology and a multi-attribute utility analysis.

The ‘Figure of Merit’ methodology has been developed by a team from the Los Alamos National Laboratories, USA. It is used to assess the material’s usability for the construction of a nuclear explosive device by a nation or a sub-national group. The methodology uses two criteria, FOM_1 and FOM_2 , in order to assess the material. These criteria include several intrinsic factors such as bare critical mass, spontaneous neutron fraction, decay heat, and dose rate. The first criterion assesses the material’s usability when the explosive yield is of little importance and pre-detonation is not an issue, while the second criterion assesses the case when nominal yield and storability are desirable. The higher the criteria value, the higher the material’s usability (Bathke et al. 2009; Bathke et al. 2012). This effectively means that the FOM_1 criterion does not take into account the effects of the spontaneous neutron emission, while FOM_2 could be used to assess the impact of even plutonium isotopes on the material barrier. The present analysis has been carried out using the algorithm applied by (Naydenov, Filipov 2015). Here, the values of FOM_1 and FOM_2 are used as a metric to investigate the change in the material barrier quality.

The multi-attribute utility analysis (MAUA) evaluates 14 utility functions linked to proliferation barriers, each utility function having an assigned relative weight. The utility functions, their assigned weights, and the complete calculation algorithm are fully described by (Charlton et al. 2007). The sum of the products of the relative weights and the utility functions’ values is used as a metric named ‘static proliferation resistance’. The sum value belongs to the interval [0;1]. The closer the value is to unity, the better the quality of the barrier. This metric is applied in a similar fashion as the ‘Figure of Merit’ criteria – as a means to evaluate the change in the quality of the material barrier. The convergence of the results obtained by the two distinct methodologies is shown by (Naydenov, Filipov 2018).

Results and Analysis

The main objective of the study is to evaluate the change in the material barrier of plutonium obtained during normal operation of a reference commercial pressurised water reactor (PWR), as a function of the fuel type (uranium oxide UOX/mixed oxide MOX), the burn-up (30–60 GWd/tHM), and the cooling time (up to 30 years), as well as to evaluate the effect of multiple

recycling, using different mixed fuel options (MOX and mixed oxide with enriched uranium, known as MIX, fuels, 356 yrs. total length of the fuel cycle). Plutonium usability is not evaluated.

The calculated FOM_1 and FOM_2 values show a general trend of decreasing criteria values, i.e. increasing quality of the material barrier and relatively small barrier quality deterioration with cooling time. Thus burn-up has more pronounced influence on the quality of the barrier. The values of both criteria have been averaged over the 30-year spent fuel cooling period in order to analyse more thoroughly the effects of the burn-up. The results are shown on Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Fig. 1 represents the change of the average FOM_1 value as a function of the fuel burn-up. A clear, almost linear decrease in the material's attractiveness can be observed for both plutonium from UOX and MOX spent fuels; in other terms, the quality of the material barrier visibly improves with the burn-up increase. The change in the quality of plutonium produced from uranium fuel is very well pronounced, especially when spontaneous neutron emission is not considered (FOM_1). The barrier quality of plutonium from spent MOX fuel basically remains constant with burn-up increase. The impact of the spontaneous neutron emission on the quality of the material barrier can be examined in Fig. 2. In that case, the quality of plutonium from spent MOX fuel also visibly increases with burn-up. In addition, the FOM_2 values are around two times lower than FOM_1 values. That observation is an unambiguous confirmation of the contribution of the spontaneous neutron emission to material barrier quality.

Fig. 1: Change of 30-year average FOM_1 as a function of burn-up.

Fig. 2: Change of 30-year average FOM₂ as a function of burn-up.

The MAUA results, similarly to the ‘Figure of Merit’ values, are virtually independent from cooling time. Because of that, a similar approach has been undertaken and the static proliferation resistance values have been averaged over the 30-year cooling period. The dependence of static proliferation resistance on burn-up for metallic and non-separated plutonium is shown in Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b.

Fig. 3a: Change of 30-year average static proliferation resistance of separated plutonium as a function of burn-up.

Fig. 3b: Change of 30-year average static proliferation resistance of non-separated plutonium as a function of burn-up.

The figures reveal that the character of the change of metallic plutonium barrier quality coincides with that of non-separated plutonium. Other significant observation is that, unlike the 'Figure of Merit' results, here the proliferation resistance of UOX plutonium is greater. The most likely reason for this discrepancy is the much greater plutonium inventory generated by mixed oxide fuel operation, which is considered in the MAUA analyses but is disregarded in 'Figure of Merit' assessments.

Another observation that can be made on the basis of the graphical data representation is that the improvement rate of MOX plutonium barrier quality decelerates with burn-up increase. Considering plutonium generated from uranium fuel, the graph can be divided in two approximately linear sections with inflexion point at 50,000 MWd/tHM, where the improvement rate decreases. When the material form is taken into account, a higher rate of improvement with burn-up is observed for metallic plutonium. However, the contribution of the material form to the overall static proliferation resistance is significant and is illustrated in Fig. 3c. If the plutonium is embedded within the spent fuel matrix, the relative quality of the barrier is between 42.8 % and 48.5 % higher, depending on the fuel type and the burn-up. The relative contribution is greater for plutonium from spent mixed uranium-plutonium oxide fuel and is inversely proportional to the burn-up.

Fig. 3c: Relative increase of the static proliferation resistance of embedded plutonium compared to metallic plutonium.

The multiple recycle is analysed only by using the FOM criteria. The examined fuel cycles are shown in Fig. 4, and further details can be found in (Naydenov, Filipov 2018a). The results from the multiple recycle analysis are presented in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. They show general improvement of the material barrier qualities, with the exception of the ‘no recycle case’ (when spontaneous neutron emission is not considered). If the spontaneous neutron emission is not taken into account (the main effect of even plutonium isotopes), it is evident that the properties of plutonium’s material barrier remain unchanged in the case of no recycle (UOX). In the single recycle case (MOX), there is a slight improvement in barrier qualities over time, mainly due to the irradiation stage. The same observations can be made in the multiple recycle case (MIX) where the highest effect on the barrier quality is observed. Once again, the irradiation stages have a higher impact. That influence, however, is the highest after the first recycle stage and incrementally decreases with each following recycle. This is due to the deteriorating isotopic composition after each following recycle, which limits the amount of burnt odd isotopes, thus limiting the impact on the barrier quality. Unlike in MOX fuel, in MIX fuel plutonium is not the main source of fissile nuclei, which also contributes to that effect. Generally, it can be concluded that the impact of cooling time on material barrier properties is relatively low.

Fig. 4: Examined fuel cycles and timeline of their stages; above: multiple plutonium recycles; in the middle: no recycle; below: single plutonium recycle. R0 to R4 refers to the number of recycles with R0 – no recycle; EFPD – effective full-power days.

Fig. 5: Change of the FOM_1 values over time in different fuel cycles.

Fig. 6: Change of the FOM_2 values over time in different fuel cycles.

Main findings and conclusions

The main findings of the various analyses may be summarised as follows:

- The material barrier of plutonium obtained by spent fuel with low to medium burn-up (30–45 GWd/tHM) is not sufficient to render the material unattractive. However, that does not confirm plutonium's feasibility for non-civilian applications;
- The quality of the barrier of plutonium generated by UOX increases linearly with burn-up (faster isotopic vector degradation) and that adds to increased burn-up feasibility;
- If plutonium's inventory is not taken into account, the material barrier of MOX plutonium is better;
- Given the results of the multi-attribute utility analysis, the material's inventory should not be disregarded in those assessments;
- Plutonium recycling in MOX improves overall barrier quality because material's decay heat, bare critical mass, dose rates, and neutron emission increase;
- An improved material barrier contributes to the proliferation resistance of nuclear fuel cycles. However, that does not imply weaker physical protection / safeguards;
- The physical protection analyses should take into consideration the properties of the material;
- The major contribution to material barrier improvement in the recycle cases is made during the irradiation cycles. Long-term decay (interim storage) has weak influence on plutonium's properties;
- Multiple plutonium recycle has the most pronounced influence over material barrier qualities;
- Overall, the decay process has a low impact on the proliferation barrier.

REFERENCES

- Bathke C.G., B.B. Ebbinghaus, B.W. Sleaford et al.** (2009) An assessment of the attractiveness of material associated with a MOX fuel cycle from safeguards perspective. In: *Proceedings of INMM 50th Annual Meeting, Tucson, AZ, United States*. Deer Field, IL: INMM, 920–934.
- Bathke C.G., B.B. Ebbinghaus, B.A. Collins B.A. et al.** (2012) The attractiveness of materials in advanced nuclear fuel cycles for various proliferation and theft scenarios. *Nuclear Technology* 179, 5–30.
- Beller D.E., R.A. Krakowski** (1999) *Burnup dependence of proliferation attributes of plutonium from spent LWR fuel*. Los Alamos National Laboratory, LA-

- UR-99-751, Los Alamos, NM: Los Alamos National Laboratory. <http://www.gammaexplorer.com/lanlreports/lanl2_a/lib-www/la-pubs/00326582.pdf> (20.01.2020).
- Charlton W.S., R.F. LeBouf, C. Gariazzo et al.** (2007) Proliferation resistance assessment methodology for nuclear fuel cycles. *Nuclear Technology* 157, 143 – 156.
- European Commission** (2016) Communication from the Commission. Nuclear Illustrative Programme presented under Article 40 of the Euratom Treaty for the opinion of the European Economic and Social Committee. COM (2016) 177. Brussels. <<https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regdoc/rep/1/2016/EN/1-2016-177-EN-F1-1.PDF>> (14.01.2020).
- Ezoubtchenko A.A., M. Saito, V.V. Artisyuk, H. Sagara** (2005) Proliferation resistance properties of U and Pu isotopes. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 47, 701 – 707.
- IAEA** (2008) *Nuclear Energy Basic Principles*. Vienna: IAEA.
- IAEA** (2010) *Technical Features to Enhance Proliferation Resistance of Nuclear Energy Systems*. Vienna: IAEA.
- IAEA** (2013) *Nuclear Fuel Cycle Objectives*. Vienna: IAEA.
- Kang, J.** (2005) Analysis of nuclear proliferation resistance. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 47, 672 – 684.
- Kimura, Y., M. Saito, H. Sagara** (2011) Evaluation of proliferation resistance of plutonium based on decay heat. *J. Nucl. Sci. and Tech.* 48, 715 – 723.
- Naydenov I., K. Filipov** (2015) Plutonium-containing civilian materials' attractiveness analysis using the 'Figure of Merit' methodology. *BgNS Transactions* 20, 124 – 131.
- Naydenov I., K. Filipov** (2018) Assessment of reactor-grade plutonium proliferation barrier at fuel discharge. In: *Proceedings of the Energy Forum 2018 Varna*. Sofia: STUPE, 127 – 133.
- Naydenov I., K. Filipov** (2018a) Change of the quality of the material aspects of the intrinsic proliferation barrier of reactor-grade plutonium in the case of multiple recycle in pressurised water reactors. In: *Proceedings of the XXIII Scientific Conference FPEPM 2018, Sozopol*. Sofia: TU-Sofia, 54 – 61.
- Skutnik S.E., M.-S. Yim** (2011) Assessment of fuel cycle proliferation resistance dynamics using coupled isotopic characterization. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 241, 3270 – 3282.

Ivaylo Naydenov
Department of Thermal and Nuclear Power Engineering
Technical University of Sofia
Sofia, Bulgaria
ivaylo.naydenov@gmail.com

**SCIENCE WITHOUT BORDERS:
ALEXANDER VON HUMBOLDT'S CONCEPTS
IN TODAY'S WORLD**

*Proceedings of the Humboldt-Kolleg
Varna, September 18 – 21, 2019*

•
Edited by:

*Lora Taseva, Radka Argirova, Dilyana Boteva,
Maria Luisa Grilli and Tăchiță Vlad-Bubulac*

•
Format: 70 x 100 / 16

•
Faber Publishing House
Veliko Tarnovo, 1 Gara Veliko Turnovo street
+359 62 600 650
www.faber-bg.com